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Research Article

**A CROSS SECTIONAL STUDY ON THE OCCURRENCE OF
GALLSTONES IN PATIENTS OF LIVER CIRRHOSIS IN
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Abstract:

Objective: The purpose of this study is to evaluate the occurrence of the gall stones in the patients who are suffering from liver cirrhosis in the medical ward of Bahawal Victoria Hospital Bahawalpur.

Material and Methods: the design of the study was cross sectional, clinical study. This study was conducted on the patients who got admission in the medical ward of the Bahawal Victoria Hospital Bahawalpur. The study was conducted on the 80 patients who were presented to hospital with the symptoms of chronic liver diseases either male or females.

Results: In this study total 80 patients were examined, in which 40 were females and 40 were males and the range of the age of these patients were 35- 65 years with the means of 43.0 ± 9.95 years. Among all of them, the patients who had the gall stones are 31%. In which the males were 14/40 (28%) and the females 17/40 (34%). The wall of the gall bladder was also associated with the edema. In out of the 80 patients twenty were the HBsAg reactive, and 60 out of eighty were the HCV reactive, however 10 were for both Anti HCV and HBsAg. 60% of the patients were pugh's in the child criteria B and in class C were 20% and no one was in class A.

Conclusion: The people who the suffering from the chronic liver diseases, gall stones are most frequent in those patients. Gall stones do not affect the survival of the patients, and mostly patients do not know about the gall stones until they do not come under any investigation. Gall-stones are more frequent in patients suffering from chronic liver disease. They do not affect the survival, and most of the patients come to know about it incidentally when they are subjected to investigations. The effective tool use for the purpose is Ultrasonography.

Keywords: Symptoms, Chronic Liver Diseases, Gall Stones, Alcohol, HBV, Cholesterol, Ultrasonography, Gall Bladder.

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INTRODUCTION:

The major reason for the mortality and morbidity in the population of Pakistan is Cirrhosis, the most common reason which is being spread is hepatitis as in comparison with the West where the alcohol is very common. In the comparison of HBV, the percentage of the HCV is higher in our country, however both can be available in one patient at the same time. Before the invention of the ultrasound machine the people who are suffering from the cirrhosis diseases, the gall stones are more common in those patients. The patients were associated with the gall stones who were suffering from the chronic liver diseases. And the occurrence of this diseases is 4 to 5 times higher than the general population and also the gall stones do not affect the survival. Gall stones are the most common biliary pathology. The types of the gall stones are different, they may be mixed, pigment and cholesterol stones. The pigment and mixed stones are normally present in quantity but it can also be single and the cholesterol stones are solitary stones. The causes for the incidence of these stones are many. For example, if the metabolism system is defected then it is responsible for the mixed and cholesterol stones. Cholesterol is insoluble in water so held in solution form by the detergent actions of bile acids and phospholipids. Bile becomes lithogenic if cholesterol is in excess with relation to bile salts and phospholipids. Concentration of bile salts is reduced in bile by increased level of oestrogens and factors which interrupt enterohepatic circulation of bile salts. The question is that in cirrhosis is it the liver or gall bladder which is responsible? Perhaps both, because liver architecture is disturbed with increased oestrogen levels, gall bladder contractility is reduced, there is a reduced bile acid pool, enhanced conversion of cholic acid into deoxycholic acid so cholic acid is replaced by increased amount of deoxycholic acid and may lead to defective vesicle formation, cholesterol is rich in these vesicles and aggregates into larger multilamellar vesicles. Most of CLD patients are not aware of gallstones. In view of these facts, an attempt was made to determine the frequency of gall stones in patients suffering from cirrhosis in Bahawal Victoria Hospital Bahawalpur.

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

In the current study we have investigated the 80 patients in which 40 were the females and 40 were

the males with a complete history of the chronic liver diseases who were admitted to the medical ward of Bahawal Victoria Hospital Bahawalpur or presented to the outpatient department of the hospital. The patients who were presented in the duration of the study was from January 2018 to December 2018 were also included in the study. The examination of all these patients are to be carried out thoroughly and confirmed that they are suffering from the liver cirrhosis. Complete examination of the blood, urine, liver functions tests, ultrasonography of abdominal and gastroscopy was carried out.

After all the examinations of the patients, all those patients were excluded who were not confirmed with the diseases of liver cirrhosis. Biopsy of liver of all these patients was not carried out. To determine the quantity of the gall stones in the patients the ultrasonography was carried out. For the diagnosis of the stones in the gall bladder the findings of the ultrasonography were three, (i) one or more of the echogenic in the gall bladder which is shadowing distally and possibly moveable structure. (ii) one or more echogenic in the gall bladder which is moveable but not shadowing. (iii) one or more echogenic structure in the region of the gall bladder which is called fossa with constant shadowing with small or no conception of the gall bladder.

RESULTS:

In the findings our study the 80 patients which are selected for this study, the range of the age of these patients was from 35 to 65 years with the mean age of 43.0 ± 9.95 years, in which 64% were between the age of 40 to 60 years, the patients who had the gallstones were 31%. So here it is important to note that the patients which were selected for this study was very selected group of patients who were admitted and presented to a tertiary care hospital of Punjab. Fourteen, out of forty (28%) males who had the gall stones and 17/40 females (34%) who had the gall stones. Difference in the percentage between these genders are not significant. ($P < 0.5$). total females were 17 in which 4 females had multiple stones and thirteen females had single stone. Likewise, the males which were twelve, out of fourteen they had a single stone and the two, out of fourteen males had multiple stones.

TABLE-I: Demographic Data (n = 80)

Total patients	= 80
M : F	= 1:1
Age range	= 35-65 years 43.0 ± 9.95 years
Positive for gall stones	= 31/80 (31%)
Males	= 14/40
Females	= 17/40
Anti HCV positive	=60
HBsAg	= 20
Both (B+C) positive	= 10

Gall bladder of the patients had edema which was obvious more in the patients with obstinate ascites. Out of the eighty patients, sixty were the Anti HCV reactive, 20 were the HBsAg and the rest ten were the both HBsAg and Anti HCV reactive. In the total patients, 20% of the patients were to be categorized in the child criteria C of Pugh's modification, however the sixty percent were to be classified to the class B and no one were classify to class A.

DISCUSSION:

In our country the major problem of health and which causes significantly mortality and morbidity is called Cirrhosis. The group of patients which participated in our study they were eighty and the range of the age of all these patients were from 35 to 65 years with means of 43.0 ± 9.95 years and also the study findings of our study were very closed to the other study which was conducted in the same city. The range of age we selected for this study is very important because the patients who are suffering from the cirrhosis diseases the complications start out in these years because these are the productive years of life. In our study we have found out that 31% of patients had gall stones but they are silent is nature because they were not bothering the patients. According to our study the percentage which we have occur from our study (31%), it is a very high figure but we have to remember that the population which we have selected for our study was highly selective population and also we can compare our study with the studies conducted by Elzouki et al and Conte De et al, according to their studies the cirrhotic patients who had the gall stones are 30% and 29.5%. A study conducted by Chung Pi Si and Maggi A et al, they reported an occurrence in high number of 41% and 38% cirrhotic having gall stones. According to the findings of the study by Sheen et al in which they reported that the presence of the gall stones in the patients of cirrhotic in which females have 31.2% and male have 18.5%. Another study was conducted in

Karachi by Razi et al in which he shows that if we calculate the occurrence of the gall stones in the population of the Pakistan than that should be 15%, if we compared it with cirrhotics it is very less percentage. Many causes are to be projected which explicate the high number of occurrence of gall stones in cirrhosis. These include alcoholism, lithogenic role of hemolysis, decreased secretion of cholesterol and diminished bile acid pool, still the exact mechanism has not been established. A possible risk in the formation of a gall bladder stone is emptying gall bladder has been suggested. High oestrogen levels may impair Gallstones in patients of liver cirrhosis gall bladder motility during pregnancy so Fornari et al suggests that increased levels of oestrogen and progesterone cause gall bladder stasis amongst these patients similar to pregnant women. Autonomic neuropathy is common in patients with chronic liver disease irrespective of etiology of liver disease. Chawla A et al also suggests that autonomic neuropathy may contribute to formation of gall stones in patients with advanced cirrhosis, perhaps by impairing gall bladder emptying and sphincter of oddi dysmotility. Acalovschi M et al and Kao CH et al also support that gall bladder contractility and emptying is markedly diminished in liver cirrhosis whereas Chung Pin Li et al and Pompili et al do not agree with this. According to the study which was carried out by Elzouki et al in which he stated that the cirrhosis patients who had gall stones are due to the prevalence of the Hepatitis however in the study of Fornari et al it has been observed that the gall stones are more common in those patients who were alcoholics. Although according to the findings of the study the prevalence of the gall stones is more common in the obese females in the age of their productivity, but according to the findings of the Elzouki et al study it has been found out that the presence of the gall stones in the males and females are equal. Maximum patients, twenty-three out of thirty-one had a single

stone however only eight out of thirty-one had multiple stones.

Severity of liver disease, is also a risk factor for gall stones in patients with cirrhosis and is thought to be another contributory factor which supports this study as multiple gall stones were more common in patients who were in child C of Pugh's classification and is also in accordance with studies of Conte D et al and Elzouki et al, that biliary lithogenesis increases with degree of liver dysfunction and could be a contributory factor for formation of gall stones amongst cirrhotic.

It was also noted that 60% of these patients were anti HCV reactive, 20% were HBsAg reactive whereas 10% of these had both viral markers. Various studies have shown anti HCV reactive in the range varying from 18%, 37.5%, 62.2% and 65.5% amongst cirrhotic and both were positive in 24.4%. Whereas in the present study it was only 10% which shows a change of pattern of viral markers.

CONCLUSION:

Presence of the gall stones in the patients who are suffering from chronic liver diseases are more frequent. These stones do not affect the patients normally; mostly the patients know about it when they came to the hospital incidentally and they are subjected to any investigation. The good tool for this purpose is which is also noninvasive is Ultrasonography.

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